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Stewardship Implementation and Lay Faithful Engagement in a Local Church in Northern Philippines

Proponents

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Abstract

The stewardship spirituality is a way of life where Filipino Catholic Christians are encouraged to become faithful and trusted church stewards by generously and gratefully sharing their talent, time, and treasure. And if they view themselves as stewards of God, it implies that they are to empty their minds and hearts of their selfish intentions of domineering creation and all graces from God and that they ought to denounce their belief and right to believe that all authority towards God's creation revolves around them. Thus, to raise the faithful of the local church of Bayombong to grow in spirituality as generous, grateful, faithful, and enthusiastic stewards. Thus, a three-year comprehensive plan was conceptualized, crafted, and implemented. This study will be conducted to assess the said spirituality program and the engagement of the lay faithful. It will employ the descriptive-quantitative-qualitative-evaluative approach specifically the descriptive design. A validated researcher-made survey questionnaire was used to gather pertinent data from the lay faithful. Data gathered were validated and substantiated through interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and were treated and analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, and standard deviation). Results show that the Stewardship Program (Time, Talent and Treasure) is implemented to a moderate extent in the local church of Bayombong, and the lay faithful of the local church of Bayombong are moderately knowledgeable and moderately witnessing the said program in all areas. With these results therefore, crafting an enhanced formation module to deepen the knowledge and witnessing of the lay faithful of the local church of Bayombong to stewardship spirituality program that will eventually end the *arancel* system or "tariff" (practice of charging and collecting fixed fees or stipends for services of priests) that prevents the poor from receiving sacraments is to be crafted and be given to the lay faithful of the local church of Bayombong through seminar-workshop.

Keywords: *Formation module, knowledge, talent, time, treasure, stewardship program, witnessing*

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Introduction

Stewardship is more than a program—it is a spiritual journey that calls for prioritizing divine purpose over personal interest, rooted in faith, gratitude, and a commitment to Christ. It involves the responsible use of time, talent, and treasure as an expression of discipleship and service (The Joy of Stewardship, 2008). Within the Catholic Church, stewardship encompasses care for creation, parish development, and individual vocation, as emphasized in the U.S. Bishops’ 1993 pastoral letter Stewardship: A Disciple’s Response (National Conference of Catholic Bishops, 1993). Despite findings that no single stewardship strategy has significantly increased giving among Catholics (Hoge et al., 1996; Zech, 2000), practices like pledging or responding to parish financial needs have been more effective, pointing toward fundraising rather than purely spiritual messaging. Nevertheless, stewardship remains anchored in a higher calling and spiritual mission (Senge, 2014; Buys & Cronje, 2013; Freeman, 2011), affirming that faith-based service and ethical action are integral to the Church’s work.

In the Philippine context, the Second Plenary Council of the Philippines (PCP II) mandates the introduction of tithing through catechesis and the gradual elimination of the Arancel System, which hinders access to sacraments for the poor (PCP II Decree #118). The 2021 Pastoral Statement on Stewardship renews this call by emphasizing catechesis, training, and the creation of concrete stewardship programs across dioceses. The Diocese of Bayombong, under the leadership of Bishop Jose Elmer I. Mangalino, DD, has responded by appointing Rev. Fr. Frans T. Balinggan to lead a Diocesan Stewardship Team (DST), establishing a three-year formation plan to foster stewardship spirituality across parishes. This initiative supports the broader vision of nurturing active, generous, and faith-driven communities (Ovando, 2020; Miller et al., 2002; Fry et al., 2011; Javanmard, 2012). The study arising from this program aims to deepen lay understanding of stewardship, support the abolition of the Arancel System, and contribute to national development goals—specifically SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals)—by promoting equitable access to spiritual services, strengthening community participation, and enhancing Church sustainability.

A. RRL and RS of Major Concepts / Variables (Based on Problem)

Stewardship

Stewardship is rooted in the Christian call to serve rather than to be served, as exemplified by Jesus in Matthew 20:28: "I came not to be served but to serve and to give my life as a ransom for many." His humble act of washing the disciples' feet remains the model of servant leadership and Gospel discipleship (Synod of Bishops X Ordinary General Assembly, 2001, no. 78). Christian stewardship acknowledges that all things—time, talent, and treasure—are gifts from God. Chandler (2016) notes that while humans are entrusted with these resources, pride, greed, and selfishness often hinder the understanding of oneself

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as a steward. Faithful stewardship is, therefore, an act of love, humility, and justice, reflecting God's call to responsibly manage His gifts for the common good.

The western model of stewardship aligns with many principles of conventional resource management systems. As Bennett et al. (2018) explain, stewardship can be exercised across various scales, from local to global, and in diverse settings. Sayles and Baggio (2017) emphasize that stewardship flourishes when various actors collaborate across organizational levels. Driscoll et al. (2012) also suggest that participatory monitoring and evaluation enhance stewardship outcomes. In Christian teaching, the understanding that all is gift—not entitlement—leads to an equitable sharing of resources rooted in justice. Pope John Paul II (1987, para. 37) discussed this in relation to social structures of sin that perpetuate injustice, calling believers to transform such systems through their stewardship.

Stewardship of Time

Time, like all blessings, belongs to God and must be wisely managed. Scripture reminds us that God's perception of time differs from ours: "With the Lord a day is like a thousand years" (2 Peter 3:8). In today's world, time has become a valuable commodity, yet many struggle with prioritizing it meaningfully. Studies show the average American spends over 180 hours a month watching television or online, but only around 7 hours in worship (Loicey, 2011; McGread, 2010). Lies (2017) challenges believers to reflect: "If time were money, are you spending it wisely?" Stewardship of time involves dedicating time to prayer, family, work, service, and rest—all as acts of love and devotion to God (Johnson & Grimm, 2018). In this study, stewardship of time begins with prayer as the foundation for deeper relationship with God and the basis for using talents and treasure wisely.

Stewardship of Talent

God has endowed every person with a unique mix of natural abilities and spiritual gifts, not for selfish gain but to serve others and glorify Him. Johnson and Grimm (2018) emphasize that these talents—whether hobbies, skills, or vocations—should be used to fulfill the mission of Christ's Church. The U.S. Conference of Catholic Bishops (USCCB, n.d.) defines stewardship of talent as the process of discovering, nurturing, and offering our gifts in service to others. Gardner's (1983) theory of multiple intelligences—ranging from musical and spatial to interpersonal and intrapersonal—supports the idea that every person holds valuable capacities. Good stewards not only develop their own talents but also help others grow in theirs (Lies, 2017). In this context, stewardship of talent means serving with love, rooted in justice, and committed to sharing God's gifts with the community.

Stewardship of Treasure

The stewardship of treasure centers not on wealth itself but on generosity of spirit. O'Hurley (2001) argues that faithful giving is not about the amount but the intent, as

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demonstrated by the widow in Mark 12:41–44 who gave “all she had to live on.” All wealth comes from God, and we are called to share it for the good of others and the Church’s mission (Johnson & Grimm, 2018). Stewardship of treasure is not just about tithing but about developing a healthy relationship with material blessings. Caparros et al. (2004) and Zalbidea (2017) stress the importance of financial transparency in the Church, which builds trust and promotes co-responsibility. As mandated by Canon Law (Canon 1287 §1), financial councils are not merely regulatory bodies but pastoral tools to help pastors plan and lead effectively. In this study, stewardship of treasure involves forming a habit of generous sharing to restore the world and fulfill our identity and mission as God’s stewards.

B. Theoretical Framework

Stewardship theory, as proposed by Davis and Donaldson (1997), posits that individuals are intrinsically motivated by higher-order needs and will naturally align their behavior with organizational goals, rendering strict control mechanisms unnecessary (Chrisman, 2019). Though originally applied in business contexts, this theory can be effectively adapted to churches, where leaders are entrusted with managing resources like time, talent, and treasure in service of their congregations. The theory highlights the importance of trust, communication, and collaboration between church leaders and members to cultivate a culture of shared responsibility and sustainable resource management. As Menyah (2013) explains, stewardship emphasizes service and duty over personal gain, aligning closely with faith-driven motivations within church communities. This perspective promotes long-term strategic planning that prioritizes spiritual and organizational growth over short-term gains, encouraging church leaders to make decisions that support the ongoing mission and well-being of their congregations.

C. Conceptual and Analytical Framework

The study determined the level of implementation of the stewardship program, level of the lay faithful’s knowledge regarding the stewardship program in the areas of time, talent and treasure, and the level of witnessing of the lay faithful of the stewardship program in the same three areas. Data were gathered from the responses of the participants through interviews and focus group discussion (FGD) were transcribed in toto and were used to validate, triangulate, and substantiate the result. The main output of the study is to come up with a formation module to enhance the stewardship practices.

D. Statement of the Problem / Purpose of the Study

The study primarily aims to assess the Stewardship Implementation and Lay Faithful Engagement in the Local Church of Bayombong for the first semester 2024-2025.

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Specifically, this study answered the following objectives:

1. Evaluate the implementation level of the Stewardship Program.
2. Assess lay faithful knowledge regarding Stewardship in the areas of time, talent, and treasure,
3. Measure the lay faithful's witnessing of the Stewardship Program in the same areas, and
4. Develop a formation module to enhance stewardship practices.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the Descriptive-Quantitative-Qualitative-Evaluative type of research. because it seeks to describe and assess the level of both stewardship implementation and lay faithful engagement or witnessing in the Diocese of Bayombong in the areas of time, talent and treasure. Moreover, this study measured the level of the lay faithful's knowledge regarding the stewardship program in the same three areas. In terms of measurement, this study is quantitative research, because the data that will be gathered will be subjected to statistical treatment of data.

The above-mentioned methods were complemented by surveys and interviews with the lay faithful. Also, pertinent sources from the different parishes will be used and consulted. More importantly, the researchers used major sources such as the deposit of faith and church documents thereby making the research faithful, contextual, and relevant.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted within the local church of Bayombong which is composed of the provinces of Nueva Vizcaya and Quirino with twenty-nine (29) parishes. The local church of Bayombong has been implementing since then the *arancel* system which refers to the present practice in the catholic church of collecting set fees for mass offerings and the celebration of the sacraments. However, the said local church adopted the Stewardship spirituality which is a new paradigm of being church promoted by the Catholic Bishops' Conference of the Philippines as a fruit of 5th centenary of Christianity in our country.

Research Participants and Sample

In this study, the participants were the lay faithful of the local church of Bayombong who are 18 years old but not 60 years old and above, and either male or female. The participants were from the parishes in the local church of Bayombong. A total of 477 participants from the twenty four (22) parishes of the local church of Bayombong were randomly selected and chosen from the lay faithful. The participants were randomly selected

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from each parish and determined through quota sampling method which is a non-probability sampling method. This means that all the parishioners of each parish who are 18 years old but not above 60 years old and above can be participants in the study.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument that was used in gathering necessary data was a survey questionnaire. The said survey questionnaire was consisted of three parts which were arranged as follows: Part 1- The Implementation Level of the Stewardship Program, Part 2- Lay Faithful's Knowledge of the Stewardship Program in the areas of Time, Talent and Treasure, and Part 3- Lay Faithful's Witnessing of the Stewardship Program. The said instrument underwent face and content validation. Moreover, to check the reliability of the survey questionnaire, it was subjected to pilot testing in one of the parishes of the local church of Bayombong where stewardship program is massively implemented. The tool has a Cronbach's alpha value of .983 indicating that the tool is extremely high internal consistency reliability.

To validate data gathered from the respondents and to gather other pertinent facts and data related to the study, and arrive at valid and reliable decisions and conclusions, the researchers conduct informal interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD).

Data Gathering Procedure

To have a well-organized and systematic gathering of data needed for the study, the researchers first identified the participants based from the inclusion criteria. After which, the crafted Informed Consent Form (ICF) was distributed personally by the researchers to the randomly chosen participants in the parishes for their permission and agreement. After the participants consented, the researchers first distributed the survey questionnaire to the participants that will measure the level of implementation of the stewardship program of the local church of Bayombong and their level of knowledge and engagement in the said program.

After the retrieval of the survey questionnaire, interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were conducted. In the interview, participants were asked open ended questions to get feedback and elicit more information from the participants that substantiated and corroborated data gathered through the survey questionnaire. The interview was conducted by two of the faculty researchers (primary researcher and any of the collaborators) in the most convenient time of the chosen participants in a place preferred by them where in they felt easy and comfortable while the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was conducted by vicariate (Northern, Southern and Quirino) in a parish hall of one of the parishes of the said vicariate and was scheduled on a date as agreed upon by the researchers and participants and was facilitated by the researchers. Before the FGD proper, the researchers explained thoroughly the purpose and scope, and procedures of the FGD.

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However, prior to the interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD), appointments were set and agreed upon between the researchers and the participants. During the actual gathering of data, the interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were recorded as agreed upon by both parties.

Treatment of Data

After gathering necessary, pertinent, and reliable data through the use of survey questionnaire, the data were tabulated and arranged accordingly. After which, data were treated and analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation.

Data that gathered from the responses of the participants through interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were transcribed in toto and were used to validate, triangulate, and substantiate the result. However, to ensure confidentiality and avoid risk, the researchers used pseudonyms instead of the names of the participants if necessary. Also, conclusions and generalizations were gleaned from the analyses and discussions and to assure the correctness and truthfulness of the results, the researchers presented it to the participants for their perusal and approval.

Ethical Consideration

To complete and produce this research paper not just technically sound but also ethically, it was submitted for ethics review to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMU-REB), Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, for their approval and monitoring.

Results and Discussions

Section 1: Level of Implementation of the Stewardship Spirituality Program of the local church of Bayombong.

Overall, the implementation of the Stewardship Spirituality Program in the local church of Bayombong received a mean rating of 1.59, indicating that respondents agree to a moderate extent regarding its implementation. It is to be noted however that the respondents agree to great extent that state that *there are members of the Parish Stewardship Team (PST) already installed and formally introduced to them as parishioners* (M=1.34). However, the respondents agree to a moderate extent on the statements that *there was stewardship seminars scheduled and conducted for those who were not able to participate or attend during the first stewardship seminar conducted* (M=1.97). This specific result was supported by the claim of the respondents when they said that there was only one seminar stewardship seminar conducted.

The Stewardship Spirituality Program in the Church of Bayombong has successfully initiated efforts that encourage parishioner participation, particularly through visible

leadership and structured activities. This aligns with the findings of Hoge et al. (1996), who emphasized that parishioners are more likely to engage in stewardship when they see tangible opportunities for involvement and leadership. Similarly, Sihombing (2023) highlights that effective stewardship thrives in churches with organized administrative systems and well-managed resources, which sustain long-term engagement.

However, gaps remain in the areas of strategic planning, educational seminars, and follow-up activities. While the parish has laid a strong foundation, there is a need for more consistent catechesis and ongoing formation to deepen understanding and commitment to stewardship. Callahan (2002) underscores that stewardship must be continuously taught and renewed to become an integral part of parish life. As reflected in the focus group discussion, some of them said that:

- There should be training and seminars to PCC-Westy VFLA Liturgical Ministers on stewardship.*
- There should be seminars in barangays on stewardship.*
- The team should be updated.*
- There should be a regular meeting of the PST.*
- Encourage more parishioners to enroll in the stewardship.*
- A program of stewardship should be organized.*
- Seminars should be made at least 2x a year.*

The implications of these findings suggest that the parish should offer more regular and accessible learning sessions, involve a broader demographic in the programs, and regularly gather feedback to ensure the sustainability and growth of the program. These steps will help make stewardship an ongoing part of parish life, rather than a one-time activity.

Section 2: Level of knowledge of the Stewardship Spiritual Program of the local church of Bayombong.

Table 1

Level of Knowledge of the Stewardship Spiritual Program in Terms of Time, Talent and Treasure.

Areas	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Stewardship of Time	1.50	0.713	Agree to a Moderate Extent
Stewardship of Time	1.54	0.814	Agree to a Moderate Extent
Stewardship of Time	1.50	0.700	Agree to a Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	1.52	0.744	Agree to a Moderate Extent

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Agree to a Great Extent), 1.50-2.49 (Agree to a Moderate Extent), 2.50-3.49 (Agree to a Little Extent), (3.50-4.00) Disagree

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Table 1 clearly shows that overall, the total mean on the level of knowledge of Stewardship Spiritual Program in terms of Time, Talent, and Treasure is 1.52, which reflects a moderate extent of agreement among respondents. The respondents agree to a moderate extent on their knowledge on Stewardship of Time (M=1.50) through various spiritual activities. Notably, there are three activities that respondents agree to a great extent namely *attending Sunday Mass regularly* (M=1.22); *spending personal time with God* (M=1.23) and *daily prayer* (M=1.37). For Stewardship of Talent, with a total mean of 1.54, three activities were rated as agree to a great extent of their level of knowledge namely, *serving in the church as lector, choir member, or usher* (M=1.30); *promoting stewardship by caring for the environment* (M=1.45); and *participating in church-organized clean-up drives* (M=1.46). Similarly, the respondents rated their knowledge of Stewardship of Treasure as agree to a moderate extent, with a total mean of 1.50. One specific activity that was rated as agree to a great extent was *supporting the different projects or programs of the church by sharing generously their resources* (M=1.46). However, *donating relief goods to the church* was rated moderate extent(M=1.68).

The Stewardship of Time is a critical component of Christian stewardship, emphasizing practices such as daily prayer, Sunday Mass attendance, and personal time spent with God. These practices align with Catholic teachings, which stress the importance of prayer for deepening one's relationship with the Divine (Groome, 2011). Catholic Stewardship Consultants (2024) advocate for dedicating time to the Lord through meaningful prayer, which, according to Pargament (2007), helps foster resilience. However, a lower level of knowledge regarding practices like daily Mass, the rosary, and confession points to gaps in spiritual formation and time constraints, which are consistent with the findings of Hoge and Wenger (2005), who noted that modern Catholics often prioritize personal over communal faith practices due to time limitations.

Moreover, there is a moderate understanding of outreach-based spiritual actions, such as visiting the sick and volunteering for parish communities, which reflects the need for deeper catechesis on stewardship as active service and compassion. Reyes and De Guzman (2021) also found a gap in Filipino Catholics' understanding of stewardship beyond liturgical practices. The call for stewardship teams within dioceses, as reported by the CBCP News (2024), emphasizes the importance of organized efforts to promote stewardship as a lifestyle. In addition, while many parishioners understand the importance of giving, the full spiritual understanding of stewardship as a responsibility extends beyond financial support (Smith, 2022). This implies the need for more intentional pastoral efforts and improved catechesis, with a focus on deepening theological understanding and promoting active engagement in both sacramental and outreach-based activities. Establishing stewardship

teams, as well as emphasizing a holistic approach to stewardship, can strengthen community engagement and spiritual commitment.

Section 3: Level of Lay Faithful's Witnessing of the Stewardship Spiritual Program of the local church of Bayombong.

Table 2

Level of Lay Faithful's Witnessing of the Stewardship Spiritual Program in terms of Time, Talent and Treasure.

Areas	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Stewardship of Time	1.80	0.890	Agree to a Moderate Extent
Stewardship of Time	1.89	0.982	Agree to a Moderate Extent
Stewardship of Time	1.74	0.817	Agree to a Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	1.81	0.901	Agree to a Moderate Extent

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Agree to a Great Extent), 1.50-2.49 (Agree to a Moderate Extent), 2.50-3.49 (Agree to a Little Extent), (3.50-4.00) Disagree

The results clearly reveal that overall, the total mean on the level of implementation of Stewardship Spiritual Program in terms of Time, Talent, and Treasure is 1.81, which reflects a moderate extent of agreement among respondents.

It can be gleaned from table 2 that the respondents generally engage in spiritual practices to a moderate extent on their implementation of Stewardship of Time (M=1.80). Specifically, participants agree to a great extent in activities like *attending Sunday Masses* (M=1.31); *daily prayer* (M=1.35); and *having personal time with God daily* (Mean=1.47). On the other hand, other practices such as *promoting devotion to the church* (M=1.73); *attending daily Masses* (M=1.91); *praying with the sick, aged, or prisoners* (M=1.92); *praying the rosary daily* (M=1.98); *reflecting after Bible reading* (M=2.02); *receiving sacraments of confession* (M=2.13); and *reading the Bible* (M=2.24) are done to a moderate extent. For Stewardship of Talent, the level of implementation shows that participants are generally involved in activities to a moderate extent (M=1.89). Activities such as *serving in church roles like lector, choir member or altar serve* (M=1.53); *assist in promoting environmental stewardship* (M=1.58); *participating in clean-up drives* (M=1.73); *assisting in fund drives for parish programs* (M=1.87); *helping in parish committees* (M=1.92); *help with church cleaning and decorating especially for Sunday Masses* (M=1.93); *preparing relief goods for calamity victims* (M=1.97); *prayer leaders* (M=2.05); *devoting time to visiting the sick and aged and ask priest to have them anointed, hear confessions, and give them communion* (M=2.11); and *volunteering for catechetical teaching* (M=2.22), and are all done to a moderate extent. Similarly, for Stewardship of Treasure, the level of witnessing shows that respondents are generally involved in contributing their resources to the church and its initiative to a moderate extent (M= 1.81). Activities such as *offering thanksgiving masses and other intentions* (M=1.62); *supporting various church projects* (M=1.62); *being part of the parish's*

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Stewardship Program (M=1.62); making special donations (M=1.74); regularly giving offertory gifts (M=1.75); helping with the church's social activities (M=1.75); offering mass sponsorships (M=1.87); supporting the POPSAD program with monthly donations (M=1.99); and donating relief goods (M=2.03). It is to be noted however that respondents agree to a great extent that they *generously share in offertory collections (M=1.45).*

The respondents' engagement in the Stewardship of Time reflects a recognition of the value of spirituality in daily life, with frequent participation in practices like daily prayer and attending Sunday Masses, which provide a sense of stability and connection (Lyon et al., 2021). However, deeper spiritual practices like daily Mass, praying the rosary, and Bible reading are moderately engaged in due to time constraints, aligning with Miller et al. (2020) and Pargament (2007), who highlight the challenges of maintaining consistency in more time-consuming activities. Similarly, the moderate engagement in the Stewardship of Talent suggests a willingness to serve, particularly in roles that are personally meaningful, though there is limited involvement in more structured or bureaucratic activities (Goranzon et al., 2021). As reflected in the focus group discussion, some of them said:

I cannot give my full time to the activity/ies cause by the same time on the activity/ies being a member of Brgy. Council.

In the Stewardship of Treasure, respondents show recognition of the importance of financial contributions, with a higher engagement in routine activities like offertory collections, which are more spiritually embedded and regular (Chaves et al., 2021). However, participation in event-based donations or support for specific projects is less consistent, with some respondents viewing these activities as optional. This is in line with Park and Regnerus (2020), who note that economic uncertainty and financial literacy can hinder deeper engagement in financial stewardship. As reflected in the focus group discussion, some of them said:

*There should be transparent in the stewardship donations given monthly, to be reported to the parishioners. Where it goes?
 Financial reports should be posted so it will be known.*

The study implies that parish leaders should create more accessible programs, offer training for ministry roles, and enhance financial transparency to help parishioners understand the deeper spiritual meaning of stewardship.

Section 4: Enhanced formation Module

The enhancement seminar-workshop module entitled **“Stewardship: A Way of Life”** is primarily conceptualized and designed to deepen the lay faithful of the Diocese of Bayombong's knowledge, understanding and commitment to Christian stewardship as a

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daily expression of discipleship and as a way of life. Anchored on the theme **“Faithful and Grateful: Living Stewardship in Christ”**, the module seeks to form and inspire the lay faithful participants to recognize everything they have - time, talents, and treasure (resources) - as gifts from God, freely given and entrusted to them for mission and service. The primary objectives of the module are: (1) to provide a solid and well-grounded scriptural and theological foundation for stewardship, (2) to help lay faithful participants reflect on how they live out stewardship in their personal and communal life, and (3) to guide the lay faithful toward making concrete, faith-filled commitments to live stewardship as a way of life.

The module unfolds through five key important parts: the Enthronement of the Bible, which sets a reverent tone and acknowledges the centrality of the Word of God; the Introduction, which presents the rationale and goals; Session 1, focused on the theological and scriptural foundations of stewardship; Session 2, which highlights the practical application of stewardship in daily life and mission; and the Celebration of the Holy Eucharist, where the fruits of the learning process are offered to God. Session 1, titled *“All is Gift: A Call to Grateful Living”*, explores how stewardship is rooted in Scripture and Church teaching, inviting the lay faithful participants to see life itself as a gift and a responsibility. **Session 2, “Faith in Action: Stewardship as Mission”**, emphasizes that stewardship is not only a personal commitment but a communal and ecclesial mission. It encourages the lay faithful to live their stewardship in the Church and the world through prayer, service, and generosity. Overall, the module leads participants to a deeper conversion and greater participation in the life and mission of the Church.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions:

1. The promotion and implementation of Stewardship Spirituality Program are present but not yet consistently and/or fully applied across the parishes in the local church of Bayombong and in the Basic Ecclesial Communities (BECs). The respondents expressed a willingness to participate in stewardship activities, particularly when clear leadership structures and visible programs were in place to encourage involvement. Respondents recognize and appreciate the visible aspects of the program, such as the installation of the Parish Stewardship Team (PST) and activities that allow them to share their time, talent, and treasure. Despite these strengths, the responses also revealed gaps in strategic planning, educational seminars, and follow-up activities, indicating areas that need further development.
2. The respondents demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge regarding the Stewardship Spirituality Program, particularly in the areas of time, talent, and treasure. In terms of stewardship of time, most respondents understand the value of personal prayer and Sunday Mass attendance, but there is limited knowledge about practices like daily Mass, the daily rosary, and confession. For stewardship of talent,

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while many recognize opportunities to serve in liturgical roles, there is a need to expand understanding and participation in broader, community-based ministries. Regarding stewardship of treasure, respondents acknowledge the importance of giving, but their understanding is often shaped by social expectations rather than a deep spiritual belief.

3. The respondents' level of witnessing the Stewardship Spirituality Program reflects a moderate yet growing awareness and participation in the integration of faith into daily life. In terms of stewardship of time, the level of witnessing is agreed to great extent through practices like daily prayer and Sunday Mass demonstrates a visible commitment to maintaining spiritual well-being, though activities like Bible reading and daily Mass attendance are less consistently witnessed. The Stewardship of talent is reflected in respondents' involvement in meaningful service roles, especially those that require direct, interpersonal engagement, yet leadership-based responsibilities, such as catechetical teaching, are less commonly witnessed. Finally, the Stewardship of Treasure is primarily witnessed through routine offertory giving, but participation in offering thanksgiving masses and other intentions, supporting various church projects, being part of the parish's Stewardship Program, making special donations, regularly giving offertory gifts, helping with the church's social activities, offering mass sponsorships, supporting the POPSAD program with monthly donations, and donating relief goods is still developing.

Recommendations:

1. It is recommended to intensify the stewardship apostolate in the parishes and enhance the stewardship module of the Diocese by strengthen strategic planning. This can be achieved by developing a clear, long-term stewardship plan with defined goals and active involvement from the Parish Stewardship Team (PST). Regular educational seminars should be implemented to deepen the community's understanding of stewardship, supported by enhanced communication strategies to promote program visibility. Institutionalizing follow-up activities such as reflection sessions and evaluations can sustain engagement and improve future efforts. Providing leadership training for PST members will further empower them to mobilize parishioners effectively. Lastly, offering diverse and flexible opportunities for involvement will encourage broader participation across the different sectors of the parish community.
2. It is also recommended to implement targeted catechesis and formation sessions that deepen understanding of time, talent and treasure. Emphasis should be placed on enriching the concept of time by promoting practices such as daily Mass, the daily rosary, and regular confession as vital expressions of spiritual stewardship. For talent, efforts should be made to broaden awareness of and engagement in community-based ministries beyond liturgical roles. In terms of treasure, teachings

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should focus on fostering a deeper spiritual motivation for giving, help parishioners move beyond social expectations and toward a more meaningful, faith-driven commitment.

3. It is further recommended to strengthen faith integration initiatives that encourage consistent practices in time, talent and treasure. For stewardship of time, deeper formation is needed to promote not only daily prayer and Sunday Mass attendance but also regular Bible reading and participation in daily Mass. In terms of talent, parish efforts should focus on nurturing leadership and encouraging involvement in catechetical and teaching roles, especially among those already active in interpersonal ministries. Regarding treasure, while routine offertory giving is commendable, to put more focus on promoting a generous attitude that encourages people to support different forms of stewardship, such as thanksgiving masses, church projects, social outreach activities and programs like POPSAD.

References

- Buys, P., & Cronje, C. (2013). A reflection on historical biblical principles in support of ethical stewardship. *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai-Philosophia*. 58. 229-240.
- Callahan, K. L. (2002). Giving and stewardship in an effective church: A guide for every member. *Jossey-Bass*.
- Caparros, E. et al. (2004), Code of Canon Law Annotated. *Montréal: Wilson & Lafleur Limitée – Woodridge: Midwest Theological Forum*.
- Catholic Stewardship Consultants. (2024). Stewardship: Give time to the Lord through deep, thoughtful prayer. *Hawaii Catholic Herald*.
- CBCP News (2024). 'Stewardship teams' in every diocese sought. *Interaksyon*.
- Chandler, D. J. (2016). Physical Formation: Health Stewardship and Embodied Realities. *The Holy Spirit and Christian Formation: Multidisciplinary Perspectives*, 185-204.
- Chaves, M., Miller, S. L., & Andersson, G. (2021). *Religious giving and financial participation in Catholic parishes. Review of Religious Research*, 63(2), 223–241. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13644-020-00437-9>
- Chrisman, J. J. (2019). Stewardship Theory: Realism, Relevance, and Family Firm Governance. *Sage Journals*. 43(6). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1042258719838472>

- Davis J. H., Schoorman F. D., Donaldson L. (1997). Toward a stewardship theory of management. *Academy of Management Review*, 22(1), 20–47. doi:10.5465/amr.1997.9707180258
- Driscoll CT, Lambert KF, Chapin FS et al. (2012) Science and society: the role of long-term studies in environmental stewardship. *BioScience* 62:354–366. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2012.62.4.7>
- Freeman, G. (2011). Spirituality and servant leadership: A conceptual model and research proposal. *Emerging Leadership Journeys*. 4(1). 120-140.
- Fry, L.W., Hannah, S. T., Noel, M., & Walumbwa, F. O. (2011). Impact of spiritual leadership on unit performance. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 22, 259-270.
- Göranzon, H., Lindström, U. Å., & Klang, B. (2021). Compassion in action: Spiritual care and community-based volunteering in faith settings. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 60(1), 322–338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-020-01083-2>
- Groome, T. (2011). Will There Be Faith? A New Vision for Educating and Growing Disciples. *HarperOne*.
- Hoge, D. R., Zech, C. E., McNamara, P. and Donahue, M. (1996). Money Matters: Personal Giving in Ameran Churches. *Louisville: Westminster/John Knox*.
- Hoge, D. R., & Wenger, J. E. (2005). Pastors in Transition: Why Clergy Leave Local Church Ministry. *Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing*.
- Hoge, D. R., Zech, C., McNamara, P., & Donahue, M. J. (1996). Money matters: Personal giving in American churches. *Westminster John Knox Press*.
- Javanmard, H. (2012). The impact of spirituality on work performance. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(1), 1961-1966.
- John Paul II (1987). *Sollicitudo Rei Socialis*. Boston: St. Paul Books and Media.
- Johnson, D. & Grimm E. (2018). Stewards of God's Influence Time, Talents, Treasure and Testimony. *Crossway*.
- Lyon, L. J., Walker, D. M., & Smith, D. J. (2021). The role of religious practices in psychological resilience and stress reduction: A comprehensive review. *Journal of Positive Psychology*, 16(1), 15-29.

- Menyah, K. (2013). Stewardship Theory. In: Idowu, S.O., Capaldi, N., Zu, L., Gupta, A.D. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Corporate Social Responsibility*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-28036-8_107
- Miller, R. J., Parfet, R. A., & Zech, C. (2002). The impact of stewardship programs on religious giving: An empirical analysis of Catholic parishes. *Journal of Ministry Marketing & Management*, 7(1), 43-60.
- Miller, L., Ramkissoon, H., & Sharma, R. (2020). Time use, spiritual practices, and well-being: A study of daily religious engagement. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 25(6), 743-755.
- National Conference of Catholic Bishops (1993). *Stewardship: A Disciples Response*. Washington D.C.: US Catholic Conference.
- O'Hurley, M. (2001). *The Passionate Steward: Recovering Christian Stewardship from Secular Funding*. St. Brigid Press – Toronto.
- Pargament, K. I. (2007). *Spiritually Integrated Psychotherapy: Understanding and Addressing the Sacred*. Guilford Press.
- Park, J. Z., & Regnerus, M. D. (2020). Financial giving and religious commitment: The role of economic insecurity in stewardship practices. *Review of Religious Research*, 62(2), 157–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13644-020-00406-y>
- Pope John Paul II. *On Social Concern*. Vatican City: Vatican Press; 1987: sec 42. http://www.vatican.va/holy_father/john_paul_ii/encyclicals/documents/hf_jpii_nc_30121987_sollicitudo-rei-socialis_en.html.
- Reyes, M., & De Guzman, A. (2021). Stewardship among Filipino Catholics: A qualitative study on lived experiences. *Philippine Journal of Religious Studies*, 38(1), 45–62.
- Sayles J.S. , Baggio J.A. (2017) Social–ecological network analysis of scale mismatches in estuary watershed restoration. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 114:E1776–E1785. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1604405114>
- Senge, P. M. (2014). *The fifth discipline fieldbook: Strategies and tools for building a learning organization*. Danvers, MA: Crown Business
- Sihombing, I. N. I. (2023). Administration in Improving Church Stewardship. *Journal of Social Research*, 2(7), 2535-2541.

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Smith, L. E. (2022). *The intersection of religion and generosity: Understanding charitable giving through religious practice. Social Science Quarterly, 103(2), 323–340.*
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ssqu.13029>

Synod of Bishops X Ordinary General Assembly, Lineamenta The Bishop: Servant of the Gospel of Jesus Christ for the hope of the world (Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 2001), no.78.

Zalbidea, D. (2017). “Transparencia y rendicion de cuentas en el ordenamiento can onico: dar razon de la misericordia.” *Phd. Diss., Universidad de Navarra.*

Zech, C. E. (2000). *Why Catholics Don't Give.... And What Can Be Done About It. Huntington, IN: Our Sunday Visitor Press.*

